

**BEST PRACTICES OF EXPERIENCED SCHOOL PAPER ADVISERS
ON HANDLING THEIR ROLES AND FUNCTIONS:
A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 8

Pages: 1049-1057

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2213

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13327361

Manuscript Accepted: 07-18-2024

Best Practices of Experienced School Paper Advisers on Handling their Roles and Functions: A Phenomenological Study

Baldwin Xavier D. Rosario,* Dhan Timothy M. Ibojo
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study is specifically concerned with the beginning school paper advisers who engaged in campus journalism without significant knowledge in handling the role and the lack of experience and awareness of circumstances like school paper management and competitive journalism. Consequently, it aims to determine the best practices employed by the more experienced school paper advisers in the province – how they select their writers, conduct trainings, and manage in school paper production. This study utilized the qualitative method of research using phenomenology, and participants were selected via purposive sampling, which trimmed down to just seven participants. Findings revealed that experienced school paper advisers select their potential writers mainly through a systematic screening process, recommendations and cherry picking best students in the campus. Some advisers found it hard to select students due to conflicting responsibilities and inclinations. Moreover, writers are trained through a rigid process while other advisers opted to invite resource speakers for the students to gather relevant knowledge in campus journalism. However, most advisers complain about the lack of funds and equipment to sustain the program; as a result, they opt to expend own resources in compensating the needs from students' meals and snacks to giving incentives and honoraria. In addition, some advisers experience stressful moments in paper production, especially that they had to regularly review writers' outputs; others have to rely to other person with much experience in layouting, so they had to shell out money to accomplish it. Despite these challenges, advisers believe that everything will be worthwhile after seeing their product that comes from dedication and hard work. Therefore, advisers adapted strategies in fulfilling the program to sustain, and the mechanisms they applied to their student writers would also hinge on the school environment, community support, and personal qualities that contribute to the success in their program. As a recommendation, it all goes back to the implementation of RA 7079 or the Campus Journalism Act, particularly with regards to the allocation of funds for campus journalism, to somehow enhance the quality of school paper advisers through seminar-workshops, partnerships, cost-reduction strategies, and student-led initiatives.

Keywords: *campus journalism, press conference, challenges, coping mechanisms, best practices, phenomenology*

Introduction

The problem to be addressed through this study is the challenge of schoolteachers who are just embarking the role as school paper adviser (SPA) with concerns to the inadequate expertise and skills, role conflict, and lack of training, that hinder capacity to give their student journalists the preparation they need for campus journalism, school publication and the competition (Paguirigan & Paguirigan, 2022).

According to Klos (2011), high school journalism programs in the United States were decreasing, with 20% of U.S. high schools were without a newspaper with reasons of school budget cuts, staffing shortages, and school administration's growing focus on test performance. Additionally, Sparling (2011) asserted the results on her national survey on high school journalism teachers' burnout levels. It was indicated that the level of emotional exhaustion and burnout are high, as job dissatisfaction and gender were its significant predictors.

In the Philippines, schools spend extensive resources for training and workshops, and teachers devote their time and effort to produce high-caliber students for National Schools Press Conference (NSPC). However, Natividad and Gapasin (2021) identified that some SPAs have problems on budget which resulted for not publishing the campus paper – as well as the support problems from school heads and fellow teachers, academic outputs as required by the curriculum, and insufficient time of training prior to press conference. SPAs were not also compliant on the selection process for their editorial board due to their numbers being insufficient, leaving those others who took upon themselves to join the program (Natividad & Gapasin, 2021).

With lack of financial and administrative support towards SPAs, a minority of schools in Nabunturan engaged in campus journalism, and only five schools out of 47 public and private elementary and secondary schools in both Nabunturan West and East districts participated during last year's Division Schools Press Conference (DSPC). The mandatory requirement of schools to implement campus journalism is not indicated in accordance with RA 7079 (Campus Journalism Act of 1991) defeats its purpose "to fully maintain the existence of the campus press" (Arao, 2013).

For this reason, it is crucial to venture and document the best practices employed by experienced school paper advisers. This way, it creates a repository of institutional knowledge that can be passed on to the beginning and aspiring SPAs, ensures reproducibility that makes it easier for others to adopt those practices and achieve similar results, and allows for the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of changes to enhance effectiveness and efficiency.

Research Questions

The study was to investigate the various aspects of experienced school paper advisers' model approaches, which centered on training and guiding beginning school paper advisers in the management of campus journalism at their individual institutions. It sought to gather first-hand information by answering the following questions:

1. What were the experiences of the participants in handling their roles as school paper advisers?
2. What were the challenges encountered by the participants in handling their roles as school paper advisers?
3. How did participants cope with the challenges in handling their roles as school paper advisers?
4. What were the best practices of the participants in handling their roles as school paper advisers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study applied the qualitative design using the phenomenological type of research, founded by Edmund Husserl, where it represents a detailed and systematic attempt to understand the structures of first person lived experience (Tassone, 2017). According to Qutoshi (2018), phenomenology is not restricted to any one approach as a philosophy or research methodology. Rather, it is more of an intellectual process of interpretation and meaning-making that is employed to gain a conscious understanding of the reality in which humans live.

By employing this method, the research described the process using bracketing as a given natural method in which events manifest to obtain an understanding of lived experiences and interpret them for meaning-making. The gathering and analysis of data happen side by side to shed light on the experience and pinpoint the observed phenomenon perceived by the participants in a specific scenario. Findings from a phenomenological investigation expand the thinking, enhance the methods of perceiving a phenomenon, and allow for forward vision and the formation of a researcher's stance via deliberate examination of firsthand encounters (Qutoshi, 2018).

Participants

In this study, the researcher chose purposive sampling to identify the primary research participants. According to Palinkas (2015), purposive sampling is a widely used method in qualitative research for finding and choosing instances with plenty of information and making the most use of scarce resources. Nikolopoulou (2022) added that these participants are selected 'on purpose' for this type of sampling because they possess specific qualities and experiences that the researcher needs.

There were seven informants in the study, who are all schoolteachers under the Department of Education (coming from public and private schools, elementary and secondary), with experiences relevant to the role for at least two years. They, too, are multi-awarded advisers and have certain characteristics or experiences and are willing to share them with the researcher (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Procedure

In this process, the manuscript and interview questionnaire underwent through the Ethics Review Committee. Furthermore, the research wrote a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent, with the attached endorsement letter of the dean of graduate school. The researcher then obtained a response letter from the Schools Division Superintendent before requesting permission in writing from the school principal. Following the request for permission, the research participants were asked to sign a consent form via face-to-face and online conferencing, informing them about the study's purpose.

Afterward, the data collection procedure with the research participants was made through In-Depth Interview (IDI). These were made possible with the interview guide for the research participants to gather concrete and firsthand information relevant to the topic under study. Research participants were interviewed in accordance with their time availability and preferred venue to avoid conflicts.

Data Analysis

Following data collection, the information obtained from the in-depth interviews were compiled, recorded, and examined.

As posted by Frogstuff (2011), data was analyzed by utilizing Hycner's 5-Step Explication Process. Although the term 'explication' is similar to the word 'analysis', but in phenomenological studies, the former term is being preferred since the word 'analysis' has a side connotation of "breaking into smaller units" that means a loss to the holistic nature of the phenomenon.

Hycner's 5-Step Explication Process facilitates the researcher's exploration of the research participants' experiences, enables the discovery of recurring themes, and offers a thorough grasp of their model approaches. It guarantees that the analysis is grounded in the real-world experiences of the participants and can produce insightful information that enhances school paper advising in educational settings.

Once the responses are gathered altogether, the researcher set aside personal biases and preconceptions to approach the data with an objective perspective. Afterwards, he carefully read the transcripts from the interview to identify distinct units of meanings, and marked and extracted these units while maintaining the context in which they appear. Then the extracted units were grouped together to form

broader themes. These group of units were themed based on its meaning. And then the researcher wrote a summary for each encapsulated themes and significant points. The summary was then shared with his research participants for validation to ensure authenticity and accuracy of the translated and clustered transcripts. Finally, he extracted general and unique themes from all the interviews and made a composite summary that integrated these themes in order to provide a comprehensive portrayal of the phenomenon under study.

Ethical Considerations

In this section, Bhandari (2021) listed some objectives which include understanding real-world phenomena, investigating behaviors, and improving lives through varied approaches. These factors contributed to preserving academic integrity, strengthening the validity of the research, and protecting the rights of research participants.

The researcher obtained informed consent from the selected research participants, ensuring that all research participants are fully informed about the purpose of the study, the benefits and risks of participating, the voluntary nature of research participation, the length of the study, the researcher's contact, and the institution's approval. The researcher also let the research participants know that their data are kept confidential, and their identities are kept anonymous, most especially that they are free to discontinue their participation in the study at any point for any reason. The research participants could also withdraw their information by contacting the researcher.

Results and Discussion

Seven schoolteachers and high-ranking personnel, identified based on their records and recognitions in the National Schools Press Conference (NSPC). They all underwent in-depth interviews; three were conducted face-to-face, while the other four conducted online. The study participants provided valuable information and data for the phenomenon under study.

Since this study required a thorough investigation and needed to address reliability and transferability concerns in qualitative research, the research employed a phenomenological research design. This allowed for an in-depth investigation through one-on-one interviews with the participants. Additionally, the data and information were triangulated using participant observation to ensure accuracy and depth.

For this chapter, the presentation sequence follows the order of the research questions outlined in the interview guide. The discussion is divided into four subsets: a) school paper advisers' experiences, b) their challenges, c) their coping mechanisms, and d) their best practices. The section highlighted the themes that emerged from the study, and corroborated with related literature and studies.

The structured themes and their emerging patterns served as the foundation for expanding the discussion of the study's findings. By connecting each to related literature and studies, the discussion was enriched to allow for a deeper exploration of their alignment with the identified themes.

Ways in Selecting the Potential Writers for Campus Journalism. The emerging themes in this structured theme were by their potentials, by personally selecting students, by the suggestions of advisers, by considering their grades, and through screening.

Findings showed that school paper advisers (SPAs) chose their students based on their capacities and capabilities to contribute to campus journalism. They were selected built from the school paper adviser's own observations or classroom adviser's annotation with the student. Additionally, SPAs considered the academic performance of the student, conceivably reflecting from their hard work and dedication that could ricochet in other tasks assigned to them. Lastly, some SPAs organized screening programs to filter out and retain the best-performing students to be included in the roster.

This has been supported in the study on schools implementing campus journalism where school paper advisers implemented selection procedure to its potential journalists (Espadero, 2022). Bradshaw (2007) highlighted the ways in becoming a journalism student, which includes reading news, being open to new experiences, knowing what the rules are before breaking them, and getting involved with everything that matters.

Ways in Training Student Writers. The emerging themes in this structured theme were by giving assignments, through intensive training, providing materials needed, through online trainings, group workshop, and one-on-one training.

School paper advisers often assigned tasks and provided relevant materials to student writers for them to study and practice their journalistic skills and the SPAs would review their output by the time they hand it in for feedback. Furthermore, SPAs conduct intensive training by organizing school-based training programs and workshops to calibrate and enhance students' abilities in the chosen event in preparation for school paper and upcoming competitions, such as press conferences. Other SPAs took advantage of online platforms to conduct training sessions with their campus journalists to keep track with their assignments. After these sessions, student writers received personalized mentoring from their coaches, who monitored their progress and offered constructive feedback and targeted guidance.

Miranda (2023) supported the idea of providing students capacity training especially that they would engage in actual journalism in their school in the succeeding years once they are geared with salient information in writing journalistic articles.

Experiences in School Paper Production. The emerging themes in this structured theme were stressful, problem with budget, faced with various challenging tasks, assigned without background in journalism, and challenging. For the participants, being a school paper adviser is indeed a stressful and challenging due to several factors which include multiple responsibilities, high expectations from other people, and other issues highlighted in the abovementioned themes. A lack of funds led to halting the production of school paper. In addition, some SPAs encountered an experience in submitting their school papers from printed articles to digitized circulation. Some SPAs suspected students used AI-powered software to generate news articles in just a click; and many SPAs struggled with the intricate process of layout and design.

With the advancement of technology, the future of journalism has changed drastically as well. This circumstance makes it easier to record events and distribute. In addition, media output made huge impact due to the prevalence of mobile phones, and it is becoming more common and revolutionary in journalism since readers do not need to buy newspapers to be informed. (Franklin, 2017).

Challenges in Selecting Potential Writers for Campus Journalism. The emerging themes in this structured theme were lack of funds, issues with training time and budget, problem with reading comprehension of writers, writers' preference with English category, being assigned in remote area, multiple special programs offered, withdrawal of writers, and learners' hesitance to participate.

The findings indicate that SPAs have been struggling with budget issues for campus journalism. This issue stems primarily from the Department of Education's (DepEd) recent No Collection Policy and the prioritization of other funding needs. In addition, SPAs have encountered difficulties in allocation sufficient training time, which is essential for students to learn and master the necessary skills and techniques.

Student writers have found struggling to remain engaged in this field due to poor reading comprehension and critical reading skills. Recruiting campus journalists has also been a challenge for some SPAs. Although many students had shown potential and interest, they often prioritized other commitments, especially as they enter high school and enroll in specialized programs.

Once students focused on specific academic goals, it became increasingly challenging to draw them back into journalism. The concern of compromising their academic performance made some students hesitant to participate in school organizations, further complicating the efforts of SPAs to sustain a thriving journalism program.

As cited by Suwanaroa (2021), the reader must be able to understand the writing system and the language, as well as the ability to interpret how words are related at the sentence level, in order to read and understand the passage. However, some English language teachers only emphasizes translation, memorization of words, and grammar rules which do not promote higher thinking skills and prevent students from developing reading comprehension (Sanphak, 2009). Because of this, Suwanaroa (2021) indicated the negative impact of poor reading ability to its self-esteem, which would affect their opportunities to land on desired jobs in the future.

Challenges in Training Potential Writers for Campus Journalism. The emerging themes in this structured theme were not enough time for training, problem with funds, not enough knowledge in campus journalism, students' commitment, students lack knowledge on basic grammar, and not physically meeting with writers for trainings.

School paper advisers often dedicated additional time beyond the regular class schedule to train student writers, as they needed to balance curriculum priorities and extracurricular activities. Effective time management was crucial for them to achieve this balance. However, many students left school immediately after classes due to the distance they need to travel between school and home, resulting in missed training session with their advisers.

To conduct training sessions, some school paper advisers even had to use their own finances, as the funds collected from the PTA were insufficient. Another challenge identified was the lack of experience among SPAs, despite high expectations from colleagues and the community for effective performance in their roles.

Lastly, the findings highlighted the difficulties of establishing campus journalism in smaller school. These school often faced challenges due to students' limited proficiency in grammar and writing conventions, which was compounded by limited access to a wide array of resources.

Indeed, such factors impacted teachers' work-related stress which are created by the responsibility given to them without the ability to make choices, as well as the lack of funds and resources to accomplish the job and restricted access to training. (Agai-Demjaha, Minov, Stoleski, & Zafirova, 2015).

Challenges in School Paper Production. The emerging themes in this structured theme were lack of equipment and expertise, smaller scope of news coverage, time management, problem with layouting, financial deficiency, and not enough time.

In producing school paper, advisers and students alike must manage not only the writing of content but also other tasks such as layout design and documentation. However, some school paper advisers lack the necessary equipment to ensure the paper's quality. When they sought assistance from colleagues, they often found little to no support. This issue is particularly pronounced in smaller schools, where fewer news events occur on campus, which made it difficult to some SPAs to fill the required number of pages in the school paper.

Moreover, due to insufficient time to work on the paper, some advisers ended up heavily editing student submissions. The lack of expertise and inadequate funding forced some advisers to use their own money to cover expenses and send their drafts to a printing press for enhancement and finalization.

It has been a clamor to most schools nationwide with regards to the implementation of Campus Journalism Act (RA 7079), particularly on Section 5 on Funding of Student Publication where it has indicated that the student publication “may include the savings of the respective school’s appropriations, student subscriptions, donations, and other sources of funds”. However, with the implementation of “No Collection Policy” has suffocated SPAs in maintaining journalism program in their school (Natividad and Gapasin, 2021).

Ways to Cope with the Challenges in Selecting Potential Writers for Campus Journalism. The emerging themes in this structured theme were focus on the positive, did not experience hardship, tap the expertise of teachers, put in place the selection process, practice writers on grammar, acknowledge the strengths of writers, and encourage the writers.

Despite the struggles faced by SPAs in selecting potential writers, their optimism and resilience were crucial in overcoming these challenges. It is worth to note that campus journalism is not a one-man endeavor; it requires collaboration. Seeking the expertise of colleagues, such as class advisers who are more familiar with students’ potentials, strengths, and inclinations, proved to be invaluable. Establishing a structured selection process also helped some SPAs to identify high-caliber campus journalists who could withstand the challenges inherent in the field.

Furthermore, building foundational skills, such as basic grammar, is essential for students to tackle more complex topics effectively. The findings also highlighted the importance of recognizing and enhancing the strengths of student writers. This way, it helps manage the issue of high-potential students who may be focused solely on special programs they enrolled. Lastly, it has been found out that it is important as well to encourage broader range of students to join campus journalism, as many students are still discovering their own strengths and may benefit greatly from the experience.

According to Kammerl and Kramer (2016), school paper advisers hold an important role in helping their students identify their strengths and areas for improvement. They are also vital in developing students’ myriad skills associated to journalism.

Strategies in Coping with the Challenges in Training Writers in Campus Journalism. The emerging themes in this structured theme were invite past journalists, use positive reinforcement, intensive training, extend extra time for training, have a winner mindset, meeting them online, and start the training early.

Findings indicated that some SPAs invited their former campus journalists to impart relevant knowledge and insights with current student writers, thereby continuing the legacy of campus journalism in their school. It has also revealed that some SPAs opt to adopt a strict approach when training campus journalists. Given the competitive nature of press conferences, discipline was the utmost thing these students need to instill.

To achieve the best results, these SPAs conducted a series of intensive training sessions starting at the beginning of the school year. These sessions, whether face-to-face or online, were designed to prepare students thoroughly and cultivate a winning mindset. The combination of rigid training and a disciplined approach aimed to equip students with the skills and mentality needed to excel in the field of campus journalism.

Advisers, together with their fellow teacher-coaches, promote student writers’ skills development and growth by providing individual coaching and training, as well as providing constructive feedback. This way, students would develop a sense of awareness and responsibility (Kammerl and Kramer, 2016)

Ways to Cope with the Challenges in School Paper Production. The emerging themes in this structured theme were build connections with others, be positive, involve student-journalists in the community, feature only newsworthy events, solicit ideas from others, utilize the help of other teachers, utilize teachers for other tasks, shell out own money, sacrifice other tasks, and identify writers from the start for different events.

Findings highlighted the importance of building partnerships and connections with other school paper advisers, particularly those who have succeeded in recent press conferences. These connections allowed SPAs to gather crucial information about updates and trends in campus journalism. Additionally, community involvement emerged as a key strategy, not only for generating unique news stories but also for immersing student writers in the broader impact of campus journalism, which involves more than just reporting what is happening in their community but also helping to resolve them. Finally, an SPA emphasized the need to feature only newsworthy events that genuinely matter to the readers.

Taking advantage on the skills and expertise of other teachers was also identified a valuable mechanism for improving school paper production efficiently. Some SPAs assigned specific tasks to colleagues with relevant expertise – ranging from layouting to illustration – and promptly identified writers for different sections of the paper. They also facilitated this process by reviewing and refining the students’ work.

Ultimately, campus journalism requires significant sacrifices. Many SPAs dedicated valuable resources, such as their time and money, to support the program. Despite the scarcity of resources and the conflicting responsibilities they faced, these advisers chose to take on

these challenges, believing that their efforts were worthwhile.

Best Practices in Selecting Potential Writers. The emerging themes in this structured theme were series of auditions, annual meeting with the principal, collaboration with local government unit, equipping of coaches, expose the writers to real world of journalism, through school-based selection, select academically smart students, and giving opportunity to everybody.

School paper advisers conducted series of auditions and background checks to identify students who would excel in campus journalism, might as well avoid issues like those experienced previously, where an SPA discovered that some students submitted premade work during the screening process. Furthermore, SPAs arranged for student journalists to meet with the principal annually to reinforce their commitment to campus journalism.

Findings also revealed that SPAs provided opportunities for all students to showcase their skills, to spot those best suited for the team. This selection process often took place at the school level. However, some SPAs opted to select academically inclined students for the field, believing their academic strengths would contribute positively to the program.

By introducing the students to campus journalism, they become more politically aware (Vogts, 2018). They would acquire a sense of understanding on matters that connects deeply to them. They would also become more informed citizens, fostering a sense of civic involvement and awareness. Through this way, students would deeply appreciate everything around journalism, how it functions and sparks connection to the community.

Best Practices in Training School Paper Writers. The emerging themes in this structured theme were invite resource speakers, implement rigid training, teach students to love journalism, train student early, mentoring with the help of past journalist, training during weekends, encourage writers to keep on reading and writing, provide learning materials, and get to know the evaluator.

Findings showed that an SPA invited former student journalists as resource speakers, who volunteered their time and expertise without monetary compensation. Another SPA invited a former journalist to mentor current student writers. All training sessions were conducted through a stern process to ensure that student writers underwent skill development to be well-prepared for competitions.

In addition, some SPAs dedicated time beyond school hours to train their writers. They also provide learning materials to enhance their reading and writing skills, purposively to expose them to a variety of writing styles, considering that press conferences feature different evaluators each year who have unique preferences for selecting the best outputs. Coaches and writers had to adapt to these varying standards, in order to guarantee that their work met diverse criteria.

Before beginning the selection process, students must understand how campus journalism prepares them to be "torch bearers" of truth (Arao, 2014), which would help their peers become more aware of issues surrounding their campus and the larger society. According to Mitra and Kirshner (2014), effective support for students' voices extends beyond simply listening to responding and working with them.

Best Practices in School Paper Production. The emerging themes in this structured theme were listen to others, full support from LGU, getting ideas from others, let students write, collaboration with other teachers, train the students, align with the trend, have a timeline on what to do, put trust on writers, and gather articles as early as possible.

To improve the quality of the school paper, it has been found essential to seek advice and apply suggestions from more proficient advisers and experts. Some SPAs collaborated with and sought support from local government units, often in exchange for providing copies of their publications or utilizing students' journalistic skills to disseminate information within the community.

Also, findings revealed that some SPAs worked with other advisers to enhance the school paper. Staying updated with the latest trends in layout and design was also crucial for SPAs to remain relevant and competitive in school paper competitions at press conferences.

Having a timeline was found to be important for keeping the production process organized. Advisers emphasized the important of trusting their writers and encouraging them to start gathering articles early in the school year. Not only did this certify a steady flow of content but also helped maintain a high standard of quality throughout the production process.

Bowen (2013) affirms that school paper advisers must empower their student journalists to take charge in creating their school paper; school paper advisers would act as facilitator, offering constructive feedback to them to improve their work. Advisers must also be adaptable when dealing with unforeseen circumstances since campus journalism involves responding to changing situations and tight deadlines.

Preparations to Ensure Victory in School Paper Conferences. The emerging themes in this structured theme were prepare for quality outputs, study the opponents, be kind, generous, and humble, attend and conduct trainings, intensive trainings, select the best students, and know the evaluators.

Findings showed that ensuring victory in press conferences involved thoroughly preparing students and producing a high-quality school paper. On top of that, SPAs consistently studied their opponents to identify their best practices, their strengths, and other factors contributing to their success. Attending and conducting intensive training sessions was also crucial for developing student writers' skills.

Moreover, understanding the evaluators' preferences was highlighted, as writing styles needed to align with their expectations. Finally, SPAs stressed the importance of remaining kind, generous, and humble, staying grounded, and honoring God for the blessings and successes achieved.

Overall, the success of the publication team and the school in general lies on the school paper adviser, who is the major human capital in an organization (Madgavkar, Schaninger, Smit, Woetzel, Samandari, Carlin, Seong, & Chockalingam, 2022). A school paper's success comes from the adviser's attributes, skills, and experience to empower students' skills, talents, and general well-being.

Conclusions

Handling the role of school paper adviser is one of the huge breakthroughs any schoolteacher can have. As much as it offers opportunities for their professional growth, it also empowers students to voice their expression without fear and inhibition. With the campus journalism as the main pillar of this study, it highlighted the best practices of experienced school paper advisers in their respective campuses. The roles and functions they demonstrated, is more than just a mere facilitator. With the experiences they encountered and the challenges they went through and overcome, is a testament that they are also a manager, a problem solver, an advocate, and a parent. Bowen (n.d.) emphasized that with the attributes of a school paper adviser being a source of motivation and enthusiasm, it would reflect to student journalists to have a positive mindset in tackling campus journalism – thus creating a conducive learning atmosphere.

Handling the advisership has also its own adversaries. With the challenges and coping mechanisms undertaken by the advisers every school year, the process seemed to be a never-ending cycle. To that effect, the central office of the Department of Education might consider looking back at the policies and legislations behind RA 7079 or the Campus Journalism Act, specifically on the funding issues that suffered many of our school paper advisers. Natividad and Gapasin (2021) firmly noted that the Act “has no teeth”, reiterating the issues with budget and appropriation of funds. Without these, the implementation of campus journalism in their schools would be sluggish. Moreover, the said law must empower not just high-potential schoolteachers or schools with journalism programs, it must reach even to farthest and smallest schools in the Philippines, by providing trainings, materials, and sufficient funds, as a head start to establish journalism in their campus.

References

- Abad-Dadayan, A. (2021). Campus journalism practices among state universities of Calabarzon. *Ioer International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 3(4). <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4108-1794>
- Agai-Demjaha, T., Minov, J., Stoleski, S., & Zafirova, B. (2015). Stress causing factors among teachers in elementary schools and their relationship with demographic and job characteristics. *National Library of Medicine*, 3(3), 493-499. <https://doi.org.10.3889/oamjms.2015.077>
- Arao, D. (2013). Reviewing the Campus Journalism Act of 1991. Retrieved from <https://risingsun.dannyarao.com/2013/01/17/reviewing-the-campus-journalism-act-of-1991>
- Bhandari, P. (2021). Ethical considerations in research | types & examples. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-ethics/>
- Bowen, J. (2013). Hiring the qualified adviser. Retrieved from <http://principalsguide.org/hiring-the-qualified-adviser/>
- Bradshaw, P. (2007). How to be a journalism student. Retrieved from <https://onlinejournalismblog.com/2007/09/25/how-to-be-a-journalism-student/>
- Cavestro (2019). Combined management report 2019 including supplementary sustainability information. Retrieved from <https://www.covestro.com/-/media/covestro/country-sites/documents/sustainability/policies/covestro-sustainable-development-olicy.pdf?la=en>
- Coletti, J. (2021). Cooper's reckless budget, Part 3: Four good ideas and a terrible one. John Locke Foundation. https://www.johnlocke.org/update/coopers-reckless-budget-part-3-four-good-ideas-and-a-terrible-one/?__cf_jschl_tk__=pmd_noD1MCLDrc4LXN5JmFIjuCk3V0uMhC9xRZiy4_jCvb4-1635768268-0-gtNtZGzNAqWjcnBszQd
- Cook-Sather, A. (2006). Sound, presence, and power: “student voice” in educational research and reform. *Taylor & Francis Online*, 36(4), 359-390. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-873X.2006.00363.x>
- Dela Rosa, J. H., Lucero, J. N., & Vargas, D. (2021). Campus journalism: varying cultures and its effects to secondary campus journalists. *Social Science Research Network*. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3794713
- Enrique Villanueva National High School (2018). Designation order – school paper adviser. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/document/412140721/designation-order-school-paper-adviser-docx>
- Espadero, G. (2022). Implementation of campus journalism in the Division of Tandag City: basis for intervention program. *International*

Journal of Research Publication, 104(1), 555-561. Retrieved from <https://ijrp.org/paper-detail/3517>

Franklin, B. (2017). *The future of journalism: in an age of digital media and economic uncertainty*. Routledge. Retrieved from <https://www.routledge.com/The-Future-of-Journalism-In-an-Age-of-Digital-Media-and-Economic-Uncertainty/Franklin/p/book/9781138305069>

Frogstuff (2011). *Analysis or explication*. Retrieved from <https://phenomenologyresearch.wordpress.com/2011/05/06/analysis-or-explication/>

Giannakoulopoulos, A., Varlamis, I., & Kouloglou, S. (2012). *Technology and journalism: conflict and convergence at the production level*. *The Handbook of Global Online Journalism*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118313978.ch16>

Kammerl, R., & Kramer, M. (2016). *The changing media environment and its impact on socialization processes in families*. *Studies in Communication Sciences*, 16(1), 21-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scoms.2016.04.004>

Kahne, J., Bowyer, B., Marshall, J., & Hodgin, E. (2022). *Is responsiveness to student voice related to academic outcomes? Strengthening the rationale for student voice in school reform*. *The University of Chicago Press Journals*, 128(3). Retrieved from <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/full/10.1086/719121>

Kinney, J. (2022). *Importance of journalism to students*. Retrieved from <https://www.unityjournalists.org/importance-of-journalism-to-students/>

Klos, D. M. (2001). *Sparking a passion for journalism in high school*. *Nieman Reports*, 55, 52-53.

Madgavkar, A., Schaninger, B., Smit, S., Woetzel, L., Samandari, H., Carlin, D., Seong, J., & Chockalingam, K. (2022). *Human capital at work: The value of experience*. Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/people-and-organizational-performance/our-insights/human-capital-at-work-the-value-of-experience>

McLeod, S. (2024). *Kolb's learning styles and experiential learning cycle*. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/learning-kolb.html>

Miranda, M. L. (2023). *Pupil's journalistic capability: basis for training program*. *Philippine E-Journals*, 10(4), 460-464. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8119837>

Mitra, D., Serriere, S., & Kirshner, B. (2014). *Youth participation in U.S. contexts: student voice without a national mandate*. *Wiley Online Library*, 28(4), 292-304. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12005>

Mohammedsalih, S. (2017). *Mobile journalism: using smartphone in journalistic work*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342546973_Mobile_Journalism_Using_smartphone_in_journalistic_work

Natividad, A. M., & Gapsin, A. R. (2021). *Public school paper advisers' assessment on the implementation of Campus Journalism Act in the Philippines*. 8th International Conference on Research in Behavioral & Social Sciences. Retrieved from <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/A25-907.pdf>

Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). *What is purposive sampling? Definition and examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>

Paguirigan, E., & Paguirigan, M. J. (2022). *School press conference coaches: their lived experiences*. *Journal of Education and Innovation*, 25(2), 1-16. Retrieved from https://so06.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/edujournal_nu/article/view/256975

Palinkas, L., Horwitz, S., Green, C., Wisdom, J., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2016). *Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research*. *National Library of Medicine*, 42(5), 533-544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>

PhilAtlas (2024). *Davao de Oro*. Retrieved from <https://www.philatlas.com/mindanao/r11/davao-de-oro.htm>

Pingol, A. (2018). *Teachers as coaches and school paper advisers*. Retrieved from <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/sunstarpampanga/20180928/281668255907221>

Province of Davao de Oro (2024). *History of Davao de Oro*. Retrieved from <https://davaodeoro.gov.ph/history/>

Qutoshi, S. B. (2018). *Phenomenology: a philosophy and method of inquiry*. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), 215-222. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1180603.pdf>

Republic Act No. 7079 (1991). *An act providing for the development and promotion of campus journalism and for other purposes*. Retrieved from https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra1991/ra_7079_1991.html

Russo, C. J., & Hapney, T. L. (2013). *Student newspapers at public colleges and universities: lessons from the United States*. *Educational Leadership Faculty Publications*. 158. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.6n.2p.47>

- Sanphak, S. (2009). Reading problems. Retrieved from <http://www.gotoknow.org/>
- Society of Professional Journalists (2014). SPJ Code of Ethics. Retrieved from <https://www.spj.org/ethicscode.asp>
- Sparling, G.B. (2011). Predicting burnout in high-school journalism teachers: An exploratory study. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Predicting-burnout-in-high-school-journalism-An-Sparling/6e27ef69b77e08f56c2b7d1e82a8b51dcd2b5cc4>.
- Stahl, N., & King, J. (2020). Expanding approaches for research: understanding and using trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 44(1), 26-28. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1320570.pdf>
- Sutton, J. (2015). Qualitative research: data collection, analysis, and management. *National Library of Medicine*, 68(3), 226-231. <https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456>
- Suwaranoa, S. (2021). Factors and problems affecting reading comprehension of undergraduate students. *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature, and Translation*, 15-29. <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijllt.2021.4.12.3>
- Tanase, G. (2013). An overall analysis of participatory budgeting: advantages and essential factors for an effective implementation in economic entities. *Journal of Eastern European Research in Business and Economics*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5191/2013.201920>
- Tassone, B. (2017). The relevance of Husserl's phenomenological exploration of interiority to contemporary epistemology. *Palgrave Commun* 3, 17066 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1057/palcomms.2017.66>
- Toshalis, E., & Nakkula, M. (2012). Motivation, engagement, and student voice. *Students at the Center*. Retrieved from https://www.howyouthlearn.org/pdf/Motivation%20Engagement%20Student%20Voice_0.pdf
- Van der Haak, B., Parks, M., & Castells, M. (2012). The future of journalism: networked journalism. *International Journal of Communication*, 6. Retrieved from <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/1750>
- Vogts, T. (2018). Effects of journalism education on student engagement: a case study of a small-town scholastic press program. Retrieved from <https://mospace.umsystem.edu/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10355/66290/research.pdf?sequence=1>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Baldwin Xavier D. Rosario, MAED-ELT

Nabunturan National Comprehensive High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Dhan Timothy M. Ibojo, PhD

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines